

DESIGNING THE MATRIX OF GR/AL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The effects of alloying elements on the Gr/Al interfacial reaction, bonding and wettability are of great importance upon designing the matrix of Gr/Al composites. Such effects of zirconium, cerium and silicon have been investigated by mechanical testing of precursor wires, single fiber tension, SEM, EPMA and TEM analyses.

The results show that the growth of Al_4C_3 can be significantly retarded if matrix contains a small amount of zirconium, and a proper interfacial bonding can be achieved by regulating cerium concentration. Silicon improves the wettability of interface when it is added into Al-Zr binary alloy, but it destroys the effect of zirconium and causes the degradation of the strength of precursor wires after high temperature exposure.

KEYWORDS: Fibers/Graphite; Matrix/Aluminium; Interface; Precursor Wires; Alloying Elements.

1. INTRODUCTION

Graphite fiber reinforced aluminium matrix composites are very attractive for structural and thermal management applications due to their high specific strength, high modulus and a near-zero coefficient of thermal expansion. However, wide spread use of these materials depends on the solutions for two major problems encountered in Gr/Al system: the first is poor wettability between fiber and matrix at the melting point of aluminium, the other is the chemical reactivity of aluminium during fabrication and service.

One common remedy to these problems is fiber surface treatments such as coating of fibers, for example with Ti-B, carbides or oxides. However, these methods

are usually complicate and with high cost.

There would be an alternative way to improve the wettability and control the interfacial reaction by modifying matrix composition. Many standard aluminium alloys have been used as matrix of Gr/Al composites, but the results are far from satisfactory. Several studies have been performed to evaluate the effects of alloying elements on Gr/Al composite properties. It has been reported that the main reinforcing phase (CuAl_2) in Al-Cu, Al-Cu-Mg alloys may have an adverse effect on the strength of Gr/Al composites when CuAl_2 precipitates at the interface during solidification and thermal exposure [1-4]. Al-Si and Al-Si-Mg alloys have good castability and are widely used in industry, however, the primary silicon phase was found to bridge between fibers and cause the degradation of composite strength [4-6]. Reports have also been presented that when matrix contains a small amount of titanium, the interfacial reaction rate is slowed and the extent of degradation in tensile strength, when exposed at elevated temperature, is obviously reduced. [2-5]

In view of the above, one basic rule in designing the matrix of Gr/Al composites is for matrix to eliminate second phases or to contain fine and dispersed second phases. Other fundamental suggestions would be indicated with the understanding of various alloying elements on regulating Gr/Al interfacial reaction, bonding and wettability. The purpose of this paper is to explore the effects of zirconium, cerium and silicon on interfacial compatibility and their impact on mechanical behavior of Gr/Al composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Material Gr/Al precursor wires (50 vol pct fiber) used in this investigation were fabricated by liquid metal infiltration. The graphite fibers were M40, manufactured by Toray Corporation. The diameter of resultant wire was typically 0.5mm.

The matrix included Al030 aluminium (99.99%Al), 0.1, 0.5, 0.9 and 3.2 wt%Zr for aluminium-zirconium alloys, 0.1 and 1.0 wt%Ce for aluminium-cerium alloys. The composition of ternary alloy was Al-0.5wt%Zr-0.5wt%Si.

Thermal exposure of precursor wires was performed in a laboratory furnace under a vacuum of 10^{-3} pa. Samples were held at controlled temperatures (400°C, 500°C, 600°C, 630°C) for 1 hour and furnace cooled to room temperature. A batch of samples were also treated at 400°C for 52h, 500°C for 6.5h and 600°C for 2h.

2.2 Experimental procedure Tensile tests were conducted on the as-received and heat treated wires. The gauge length was 50mm and the crosshead velocity was 2.5 cm/min. Tensile strength of single fiber extracted from matrix was also measured. Twenty tests were carried out each time in order to obtain

Weibull distribution of strength.

TEM specimens were prepared by mechanical dimpling and ion beam thinning. The specimens were examined in a Phillips CM12 TEM, operated at 120 kv.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure of As-received Gr/Al Precursor Wires Fractography of Al-Zr precursor wires appeared debonding at the fiber/matrix interface, and breakage of fibers as well as matrix (Fig.1a). It was observed that the length of fiber pull-out increased with the increase of zirconium content. In contrast, the failure mode of Al-Ce precursor wires were different, as shown in Fig.2a and Fig.2c, fibers broke first, followed by the ductile failure of matrix.

FIGURE 1. Fracture surface of precursor wires. (a) Al-0.1Zr, as received, (b) Al-0.5Zr, 400°C, 52h, (c) Al-0.5Zr, 600°C, 1h, (d) Al-0.5Zr-0.5 Si, 600°C, 1h.

Transmission electron microscopy revealed no obvious reaction products at the interfaces for as-received precursor wires (Fig.3). The graphite fibers have a strong texture along the longitudinal direction (Fig.3a). In the case of Al-Zr matrix, it was occasionally detached from fiber surface, indicating a weak bonding between fiber and matrix. Separation seldom occurred between Al-Ce alloy and fiber, showing a strong bonding at the interface. There are hardly any precipitates can be observed in Al-Zr and Al-Ce alloys (Fig.3). It is believed that zirconium and cerium are in solid solution due to a higher cooling rate (200°C-300°C/sec) when fibers were infiltrated.

FIGURE 2. Fracture surface of composite wires. (a)Al-0.1Ce,as-received (b)Al-0.1Ce,600°C,1h (c)Al-1.0Ce,as-received (d)Al-1.0Ce,600°C,1h.

3.2 Microstructure of Heat-treated Gr/Al Precursor Wires When Al-Zr precursor wires were subjected to a thermal exposure at 600°C for 1h and fractured, many fibers were left protruding from the fracture surface(Fig.1c),and small grains were found to adhere to the pull-out fibers. EDX analysis of these grains revealed the only presence of Al(Fig.4a), indicative of carbide phase

FIGURE 3. TEM micrographs showing no precipitation at the interfaces of as-received wires.(a)Al-0.5Zr,(b)Al-1.0Ce.

Al_4C_3 , which remained on the fiber surface after the dissolution of matrix by 20% NaOH. Fig.4b depicts the result of EDX analysis on the matrix side after the fiber had been pulled out, showing trace existence of Ar, Cl, and Ti, which arose from the CVD process. It is clear that debonding occurred between fiber and Ti-B coating. Wires heat treated at 400°C for 52h revealed the same fail-

ure mode but fibers are free from such grains(Fig.1b).

The failure mode of Al-Zr-Si wires, comparing with Al-Zr wires, is quite different(Fig.1d), fibers broke first and then matrix was strained to failure.

FIGURE 4. EDX spectrum from fractured surface.(a)from grains adhered to the fiber surface,(b)from the matrix side.

FIGURE 5. EPMA result of 600°C, 1h treated Al-0.5Zr wires. Upper curve :O, middle one:Zr, lower one:Al.

FIGURE 6. EPMA result of 600°C, 1h treated Al-0.1Ce wires. Upper curve: O, middle one:Ce, lower one:Al.

The failure mode of Al-Ce wires are similar to that of Al-Zr-Si wires(Fig. 2b, 2d), and it was found a higher cerium concentration led to a stronger interfacial bonding.

EPMA investigation on the longitudinal sections of Al-Zr and Al-Ce precursor wires showed no zirconium or cerium segregation at the interface after high temperature exposure(Fig.5,6), but for Al-Zr-Si wires, segregation occurred both for zirconium and silicon, as shown in Fig.7. Zirconium and silicon may form compounds, distributing in the matrix and at the interface, this points to the fact that silicon had most likely accelerated the precipitation of zirconium, thus destroyed the effect of zirconium. Consequently, the mechanical property of precursor wires was also impaired.

It is generally agreed that products of interfacial reaction increase the chemical bonding of interface and in turn degrade mechanical properties of composites[7,8]. TEM observations confirm the presence of reaction products

FIGURE 7. EPMA result of 600°C
1h treated Al-Zr-Si wires.

Upper curve: Zr

Lower curve: Si

at interfaces for thermal exposed precursor wires (Fig. 9-11). Less frequently, Al-Zr and Al-Ce compounds were found to precipitate at the interface. Fig. 8 exhibits $CeAl_4$ precipitating at the interface and its size is about $0.2 \mu m$. The extent of reactions at the interface varied considerably for Al-Zr and Al-Zr-Si precursor wires. The growth rate of Al_4C_3 is retarded when the matrix is Al-0.5Zr (Fig. 10), however, at the interface of Al-Zr-Si precursor wires, Al_4C_3 grows at a higher rate and a large fragile phase is formed even the specimen was thermal exposed for a shorter time (Fig. 13). Al_4C_3 growth was also observed in Al-Ce wires, but less severe compared with Al-Zr-Si wires. The growth pattern of Al_4C_3 in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 suggests that there may be a nucleation stage at the beginning of growth, and Al_4C_3 may have a crystal relationship with matrix.

FIGURE 8. TEM micrograph of Al-1.0
Ce precursor wire, 600°C, 1h treated,
Showing $CeAl_4$ precipitation at the
interface.

FIGURE 9. TEM micrograph of Al-0.1
Zr precursor wire, 600°C, 1h treated,
showing the twin growth of Al_4C_3 .

It has been reported previously that zirconium and cerium can improve the toughness of aluminium alloys, and the above observations suggest that toughness of the matrix plays an active role on the properties of Gr/Al composites.

3.3 Mechanical properties Table 1 shows the effect of time and temperature

on the tensile strength of precursor wires. For matrix of pure aluminium, the measured strength declines from 87 percent of the rules of mixtures (ROM) for as-received precursor wires to about 55 percent of ROM for specimens thermal exposed at 600°C,1 hour. In comparison, the strength increases when

FIGURE 10. TeM micrograph of Al-0.5Zr precursor wire 600°C,2h treated.

FIGURE 11. TEM micrograph of Al-Zr-Si precursor wire, 600°C,1h treated, showing significant growth of Al_4C_3 .

matrix was doped with zirconium. For wires containing 0.5Zr, the strength remains over 80 percent of ROM after thermal exposure at 600°C,1 hour. As can be seen in Table 1, there is a best concentration of zirconium in matrix. On the other hand, the wettability between fiber and matrix was enhanced when 0.5Si was doped into Al-0.5Zr alloy. However, the strength decreased drastically after high temperature exposure, although the as-fabricated wires showed comparable strength with other precursor wires.

It was found that the tensile strength decreased with the increase of cerium concentration in matrix and severe loss of strength was observed via thermal exposure of these composite wires. Previous observations indicated a strong interfacial bonding and less severe interfacial reaction. How cerium affects composite properties need further investigation.

Table1 Tensile Strength of Precursor Wires(Gpa)

matrix	Al030	0.1Zr	0.5Zr	0.9Zr	3.2Zr	0.5Zr-0.5Si	0.1Ce	1.0Ce
RT	1.18	1.12	1.25	1.19	1.19	1.15	1.15	0.96
400°C1h	1.04	1.09	1.25	1.13	1.22	1.16	1.04	0.94
400°C52h	1.03	1.02	/	/	1.16	/	/	/
500°C1h	0.94	1.12	/	1.15	1.21	1.01	/	/
500°C6.5h	0.88	1.11	/	1.03	1.16	0.96	/	/
600°C1h	0.76	0.88	1.13	0.80	0.85	0.56	0.80	0.61
630°C1h	/	0.61	/	/	0.51	0.37	/	/

The results of single fiber tension are presented in Table 2. It can be noticed while the strength of precursor wires decreased apparently when the exposure temperature exceeded 500°C, the fiber strength only slightly decreased after exposure at 600°C, 1 hour, but degraded quickly at higher treatment temperature. This indicated that fibers were severely attacked due to excess interfacial reaction. At lower treatment temperature, Al_4C_3 might form and act as source of crack without degrading the intrinsic strength of fibers dramatically. Such difference may also be ascribed to the intrinsic defects in precursor wires and non even fiber distribution.

Table 2 Tensile Strength of Extracted Fibers(Gpa)

matrix	0.1Zr	0.5Zr-0.5Si	0.1Ce	M40,600°C binder burning
as-received	2.44	2.39	2.34	
400°C 1h	2.36	2.22	2.28	
500°C 1h	2.24	2.17	2.24	2.68
600°C 1h	2.24	2.12	2.20	
630°C 1h	1.51	1.22	1.30	

The above observations suggest that matrix alloying is an efficient but easy way to enhance wettability and avoid excess interfacial reaction. An obvious requirement in order to optimize the matrix of Gr/Al composites is to accumulate data of various alloying elements on the effects of interfacial wettability, bonding and reaction. Further work need to be done on ternary or more components aluminium alloys in order that a specific matrix can be designed.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1). Matrix alloying is a useful way in regulating interfacial reaction, bonding and wettability of Gr/Al composites. A proper and stable interface

can be achieved via modifying the type and content of elements, which in turn allow the full use of fiber properties.

- 2). Excellent precursor wires were obtained when matrix was doped with a small amount of zirconium, the strength was over 80% of ROM after Al-0.5Zr wires were subjected to thermal exposure at 600°C for 1 hour.
- 3). Over saturated zirconium in the matrix weakened the interfacial bonding and slowed down the growth rate of Al_4C_3 .
- 4). Adding cerium into matrix resulted a strong interfacial bonding, which led to the premature failure of fibers.
- 5). The interfacial wettability was improved by silicon doping into Al-Zr matrix, but silicon promoted the decomposition of Al-Zr solution and impaired the effect of zirconium, resulting a low quality of composite wires.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors very much appreciate Mr.L.F.Zhou and Mrs.H.M.Huang for their technical skills in preparation of precursor wires. They are also very grateful to Mr.W.J.Jiang for the microstructural examinations.

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